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Assessing the impact of women's enterprises on household livelihoods and survival: Evidence from the North West Region of Cameroon

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The microenterprise sector has emerged as a major strategy to address the issues of unemployment and poverty challenging most developing economies. With limited alternatives to generate income on offer, the sector has become an attractive strategy to enhance the livelihoods of the poor as it provides low-income people with the opportunity to undertake income generation. Inspired by recent debates on the role of women's micro enterprise activity, the paper examines women's contribution to household survival through their enterprise activity. Drawing on empirical data from the North West Region of Cameroon, the study confirms that WMSEs are central to the economic prospects of a majority of female entrepreneurs. These enterprises offer the sole source of income for these households and are strategic in meeting the basic household needs. The paper also argues that whilst women's enterprises provide a safety net for household survival and a springboard for women's economic participation, entrepreneurs remain trapped in traditional, low return activities.

Key words: women's enterprises, livelihoods, household survival

1. INTRODUCTION

The micro and small scale enterprise (MSE) sector has within the past three decades gravitated into the mainstream within development debates. Research on micro and small scale enterprise (MSE) activities underscores the centrality of the sector as a major source of employment and a way to enhance income streams for the poor (Servon and Bates, 1998; Sethuraman, 1998; Mead and Liedholm, 1998; Liedholm, 2002; Greeley, 2006; CGAP, 2003). Through numerous self-employment opportunities for the poor, the MSE sector is seen as a means of making the poor economically active. The volume of activity in the sector and given that these activities are considered as a major source of employment for the poor is evidence of the substantial number of livelihoods that are dependent on these activities. Much of the discussions on MSEs indicate the proliferation of women with the expansion of WMSEs becoming a common phenomenon particularly in developing countries. Whilst women's micro and small scale enterprises (WMSEs) are instrumental in facilitating the economic participation of poor female entrepreneurs, these activities are strategic in meeting basic needs and ensuring household survival as benefits are also directly linked to meeting different household needs in terms of their contributions to healthcare, nutrition, and education (Hashemi, 2004; Mahmud, 2003; Greeley, 2006). This evidence lays the ground for some optimism in the role of WMSE activities as a major source of survival.

Section 2 of the paper provides an analysis of the profile and livelihood activities of female entrepreneurs in the study sample. Section 3 provides a review of factors motivating female entrepreneurs' entry into the MSE sector. In particular, the section will explore the aims and objectives of female entrepreneurs and reasons for engaging in the chosen activity. In section 4, discussions present a detailed analysis of the various household expenditure and consumption needs and household provisioning achieved with the aid of income generated from an MSE activity. Finally, section 5 provides a general conclusion to the paper.

Methodology

This paper presents an analysis of field research conducted with 45 female entrepreneurs in the North West Region of Cameroon. Primary data, which constituted the principal source of information for the study was elicited using multiple data collection methods. I used a combination of semi structured interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs) and oral histories, conducted primarily in Pidgin English, to generate data. The interviews were used to solicit demographic information from entrepreneurs. Together with FGDs and oral histories, the

interviews also captured the motives of entry into business and reasons for operating particular business ventures including the importance of income earned for meeting basic household needs.

2. THE PROFILE AND LIVELIHOOD ACTIVITIES OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURS IN THE MSE SECTOR

Marital status of female entrepreneurs in the MSE sector

The socio-demographic details of respondents in the study sample illustrate some heterogeneity and variations in the characteristics of women engaged in income generating activities in the micro and small scale enterprise sector. Information about the marital status of respondents in the sample, as can be seen on Table 1 below, shows that a majority (27) of respondents in the sample, that is 60%, are married, although a significant number are nonetheless female heads of households.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by marital status

Married		Single	Widow	Total
Spouse absent from home	Spouse present at home			
3 (6.7%)	24 (53.3%)	14 (31.1%)	4 (8.9%)	45 (100%)

Source: Generated from field interviews and life histories

Overall, about half the number (21; that is, 46.7%) of respondents in the sample are female heads of households. These are made up of entrepreneurs who are single, widowed or married with spouses or partners away from home; highlighting the breadwinner position of women in these households. For all female headed entrepreneurs in the study, meeting basic needs of household members is the major responsibility and duty of all. It is worth noting that although a little over half (24) of entrepreneurs appear to be married with a male partner present at home as shown on Table 1 above, meeting basic needs in some of these households is nevertheless the sole responsibility of the female entrepreneur, because of the lack of employment of the spouses. Out of the 24 married female entrepreneurs living together with their partners, 7 (26%) of the partners are non-working and non-earning because they are either sick, retired and/or retrenched (Table 2 below), making the households more dependent for survival on the female entrepreneur.

The occupational status of spouses of female entrepreneurs

As shown below, data on Table .2 illustrate that only 4 out of 27 of spouses of women in the sample have paid employment in the formal sector as civil servants.

Table 2: A Distribution of the Occupational status of respondents' partners

Formal Employment	Occupation						Total
	Self Employment			Unemployed			
	Farming	Business	Others	Retired	Sick	Retrenched	
4 (14.8%)	2 (7.4%)	6 (22.2%)	8 (29.6%)	3 (11.1%)	1 (3.7%)	3 (11.1%)	27 (100%)

Source: Generated from field interviews and life histories

What is noteworthy about the occupational status of the partners of respondents in the study is the fact that, like their wives, most spouses are also engaged in different forms of self-employment. As indicated on Table 2 above, a greater majority (59%) of the spouses of female entrepreneurs in the study are self employed followed by 26% who are unemployed with only 15% of spouses in paid or salaried formal sector employment as teachers, clerks and cashiers. Other income earning and self-employment activities of spouses reported by respondents in the sample include farming and various small business activities such as, tailoring, rickshaw pulling, driving, carpentry, building and mechanics. Although these activities are created and operated to generate a source of income for the men and their families, like women's income earning and self-employment activities, there may also exist a likelihood of uncertainty and irregularity in terms of their daily income earning capacity and capability. Thus, it is quite evident that income generated by women from their MSE activities will be very crucial in supplementing husbands' incomes in meeting household needs. Given that 26% of partners are non-working and

non-earning, and the fact that approximately 47% (Table 2 above) of households are female headed (de facto and de jure), it is obvious that ensuring household survival and meeting the basic needs of members of these households is in reality the role of the women. Being the principal source of income in the household, it goes without saying therefore that female entrepreneurs are also practically the major and (in some cases) the sole providers of household welfare needs for household members.

Level of education of respondents in the sample

The educational background of respondents in the sample studied show that most women entrepreneurs have barely finished primary education or are school drop outs with some secondary education, a fundamental and significant limitation for employment into formal sector jobs. The highest level of education attained by respondents was up to the secondary school level as shown on Table 3 below.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by level of education

Level of Education of Respondents					Total
No primary	Primary	Some Secondary	Ordinary Level	Post secondary	
1 (2.2%)	16 (35.6%)	19 (42.2%)	9 (20%)	0	45 100%

Source: Generated from field work

Other studies conducted in Cameroon (Fonchingong, 2005; Niger-Thomas, 2001; and Forje, 1998) and in Zimbabwe (Muzvidziwa, 2000) also confirm that female micro entrepreneurs and self-employed women in general have relatively low levels of education with very few women in the sector who have attained some post - econdary education.

Evidence from the in-depth interview confirms very low paid formal employment opportunities for women in the sample in terms of previous working experience. With respect to previous working experience, only a limited number (5 out of 45 or 11%) of respondents in the study sample had been in paid employment before taking up self-employment. The few entrepreneurs with previous working experience were previously employed as secretaries, clerks and auxiliary ward servants and nurse: typical low salaried jobs. As for training, only entrepreneurs involved in consumer services (hair dressing and tailoring or dress making) had related on-the-job training as apprentices, meanwhile entrepreneurs in commercial services received no training.

Age of respondents in the sample

As shown on Table 4 below, a majority of entrepreneurs in the sample are relatively young. More than three quarters of interviewees in the sample are women between the ages of 20-50 years. An analysis of the age distribution of entrepreneurs in the sample by access to enterprise support reveal that all entrepreneurs without access to enterprise support are aged between 20 and 50 years with only 16% of entrepreneurs in this category above the age of 40 years.

Table 4: Distribution of entrepreneurs by age

Age range (years)	Total	
	N	%
Less than 20	0	0
20-30	15	32
31-40	15	32.5
41-50	10	23
More than 50	5	12.5
Total	45	100

Source: Generated from field data

It is rather an important finding that on average, 87.5% of entrepreneurs who are into MSE activities in the sample studied are below 50 years; a period during which entrepreneurs' business activities may coincide with child bearing and childrearing responsibilities. This relatively young age of female entrepreneurs is also reported by Fonchingong (2005) in a study of food vendors in the South West Province of Cameroon, where close to 90% of entrepreneurs involved in food vending in the province are 50 years and below. In the same way, this tendency

of young female entrepreneurs in the MSE sector in Cameroon is consistent with other studies in other parts of Africa and Asia. On average, 87% of female entrepreneurs in Bangladesh, Philippines, Tunisia, Tanzania and Zimbabwe are aged 50 years and below (Marcucci, 2001; ILO, 2003). A possible explanation for this trend in the sample may be related to the motive of entry into self employment. Prompted by economic hardship, entrepreneurs are compelled to combine childcare and childrearing tasks and income earning opportunities because of the need to supplement meagre household incomes. This confirms that the entry of women into the MSE sector is mainly for economic need and survival grounds. Thus, in conformity with Kabeer's (1997) views, women's entry into self employment and income earning opportunities is by and large associated with their life cycle, household status and economic status.

Household size of female entrepreneurs in the sample

Considering the household size of entrepreneurs in the study sample, information and data collected through the in-depth interviews captured the number of dependants living in each household. All dependants are considered as household members including children and extended family members who do not earn an income and therefore depend on the head of household for basic survival needs and livelihood. Taking this into consideration, a majority of entrepreneurs in the sample have an average family size of five household dependants as shown on Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Distribution of dependents per household in the sample
Source: Generated from Field Data

Overall, 77.8% of respondents in the sample had 1-5 dependants, with only 17.8% with more than 5 dependants. Only 4.4% of respondents have no dependants. The greater the number of dependants, the greater childcare responsibilities for women on the one hand. On the other hand the higher the number of dependants per household, the higher the availability of unpaid family labour.

Size of WMSE activities

Looking at the size of women's MSE activities, evidence from the sample indicates that women's micro and small scale enterprises have less than 10 employees (excluding the entrepreneur in question). In terms of number of employees, MSEs in Cameroon are enterprises with 0-10 employees (MINASCOF, 1997). The findings from the interviews (see Table 5 below) reveal that WMSEs are micro scale with a majority (93.4%) of women's enterprises concentrated in the 0-5 continuum of MSEs. The majority of employees of women's MSEs in the sample are apprentices.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by number of employees/apprentices

Employees/ Apprentices	Total	
	n	%
0	30	66.7
1-5	12	26.7
6-10	3	6.7
> 10	0	0
Total	45	100

Source: Generated from field work

Apprentices are common with MSE activities providing consumer services such as hair dressing and tailoring or dress making. Worth mentioning is the fact that enterprises predominating the 0-5 band are sole proprietorships (67%), run and operated by a single entrepreneur without any employees or apprentices. It is also worth noting that apart from enterprises providing services (particularly consumer services) such as hair dressing and dress making as mentioned above, the group of micro enterprise activities that are sole proprietorships consist of activities such as petty trading, small-scale retailing, and catering (restaurants). It will therefore not be surprising that for these sole proprietorships, the labour force is commonly characterised by unpaid family labour.

Considering the size of women's enterprises in terms of capital, it is obvious that enterprises of respondents in the sample studied are micro scale with very meagre initial capital as shown on the table below. As shown on Table 6 below, more than half of entrepreneurs have a start up capital of less than 100,000fcfa with only 10% and 8% of respondents in the sample with an initial capital of more than 400,000fcfa respectively. As for entrepreneurs' current working capital, while close to half (52%) of respondents without access to enterprise support services had a working capital of 300,000fcfa and more only about 20% of entrepreneurs with access to enterprise support services and micro credit are in this category. Thirty five per cent of respondents with access to enterprise support indicated the inability to determine the current working capital of their MSE activity raising the flaws and weaknesses in female entrepreneurship. This also affirms business management and book keeping as obstacles for female entrepreneurs in Kenya, who encounter difficulty determining and recording changes in sales, business output and general profit maximisation potential of MSE activities (Mead and Liedholm, 1998).

Table 6: Distribution of respondents by initial and working capital

Amounts (thousands of FCFA)	Initial Capital		Current Working capital	
	n	%	n	%
< 50	15	33.3	2	4.4
50-100	12	26.7	8	17.8
>100<200	10	22.2	7	15.6
>200<300	1	2.2	2	4.4
>300<400	3	6.6	5	11.1
>400	4	8.8	12	26.7
No response	0	0	9	20
Total	45	100	45	100

Source: Data compiled from field data

As shown on Table 6, slightly more than half of the respondents have an initial and working capital of up to 100,000fcfa. A number of studies indicate that women are more concentrated in the MSE sector and are able to start up micro and informal businesses because of the small start-up capital requirements of enterprises in the sector. The small start-up or initial capital of WMSEs meets one of the characteristics enumerated by Mayoux (1995), Soetan (1997), Kevane and Bruce (2001) and Liedholm (2002), as a major determinant of women's involvement and influx into micro and small scale businesses.

Composition of WMSE activities

Among the different MSE activities operated by women in the study, five different activities were identified as most customary and more prevalent; petty trading, hair dressing, tailoring or dress making, catering (restaurants) and second hand clothes vending. From the preceding list of MSE activities operated by female entrepreneurs, it is clear that in terms of category, women's enterprise initiatives are mostly in commerce and services (consumer). To be more specific, results from the study suggest that 67% of respondents in the sample studied are primarily engaged in commerce (restaurants, retail trade, petty trading, off-licence, second hand clothes vending). The fact that these activities involve the sale of either goods and/or services, make them commercial than production oriented in nature (Kevane and Wydick, 2001; Wydick, 1999). On the other hand, 33% of MSE activities of respondents in the sample comprise of consumer services such as hair dressing and tailoring.

Looking beyond the two broad categories of commercial and consumer service activities, it is clear from Figure 2 below that WMSE activities are heavily concentrated in petty trading as the largest simple proportion of 10 out of 45 (22%) respondents are involved in petty trading activity. The reason for women's concentration in petty trading can be as a result of the little capital required to start up a petty trading business which is confirmed by the data on size of initial capital (Table 6). Also, another plausible explanation for the concentration of women in petty trading activities, which may also be true for other commercial activities in the study (restaurants, second hand clothes vending) could be the limited financial and human capital requirements involved to set up a commercial activity. Setting up a commercial activity requires neither training nor apprenticeship, making entry into such activities relatively cheaper than for consumer services (hair dressing and tailoring) where time and money is spent on training/apprenticeship. Although other MSE activities like restaurants may also need smaller start-up capital, this activity involves more labour input and time (Krieger, 2000) and therefore may attract fewer entrepreneurs.

Figure 2: Distribution of MSE activities in the sample
Source: Generated from field data

Several factors and variables emerged in association with the type of activity operated. First, the type of labour supply and age of the entrepreneur appear to be two fundamental explanatory variables to the type and composition of activity operated. As revealed by empirical data, operators of hairdressing saloons and dress making or tailoring are entrepreneurs who are relatively younger than the others in the sample with an average age of 33 years and 31 years for entrepreneurs in hair dressing and dress making respectively. This finding is consistent with a similar study in Tanzania, where more than 80% of female entrepreneurs operating in the beauty care sector are between the ages of 20-40 years. This tendency can be explained by the predisposition and likelihood to find younger (rather than older) women who are more interested in fashion and beauty (ILO, 1998).

The results of this study are consistent with other studies in relation to the composition of women's MSE activities in other parts of Africa and Latin America. In Kenya, Nigeria, Zimbabwe and Dominican Republic, women's MSE activities are more or less sole proprietorships. It is also very typical that in terms of composition, women's enterprises in these countries predominate in activities such as petty trading (Liedholm, 2002;

Muzvidziwa, 2000; Mead and Liedholm, 1998). Also, in Cameroon, as Fonchingong (2005) and Niger-Thomas (2001) note, most of women's income earning opportunities are particularly common in the area of petty trading as a result of the ease to start and the relatively low capital needed to operate these activities.

3. MOTIVES FOR ENTRY AND BUSINESS OBJECTIVES OF FEMALE MICRO ENTREPRENEURS

A number of factors come into play with respect to the decision and rationale of taking up self employment or creating an MSE or income earning activity. Taking into account considerable variations that exist in the needs and concerns of different individuals, it is also commonplace that individuals may possibly display and are pushed by a range of reasons into self employment with a variety of objectives and goals they aspire to achieve. Hence the motives of entry into business and business objectives will vary from one entrepreneur to the other and with different activities. The type of activity to run or operate may also depend on the ability, skills and capacity of the individual, including the resource requirements and needs of the enterprise and how easily these are accessible. While the decision to be self employed or to operate an MSE activity may be influenced by changes in ones' personal life situation, family cycle or work history, others could be spurred on by other financial and economic pressures into the MSE sector or self employment as will be discussed below. There are however, varying explanations provided by respondents as a push factor or justification of entry into MSE activities.

An analysis of the data collected through the in-depth interviews reveals various motives and factors presented by entrepreneurs as responsible and playing a significant role in making them take up self employment and income earning opportunities, as summarised in Table 7 below. The most common motive of entry into business mentioned by entrepreneurs is as a result of hardship. In relation to the potential implications of the economic crisis and SAP policy measures (job loss, state withdrawal from social services, etc), respondents in the study sample experienced difficulties for one reason or the other to meet basic needs and therefore took up self employment as an option to earn survival. Widows and single women represent respondents who were more or less motivated into business by hardship than their married counterparts.

Table 7: Motives of entry into business

Business Motive	Frequency N	Percentage
Idleness caused by being unemployed	8	17.5
Love of business (hobby)	11	24
Encouraged by family	11	24.5
Need for extra income for household needs	27	60
Need for personal income	30	65.5
Hardship	37	82.5

Source: Generated from field interviews

As can be seen from the following testimonies of some respondents in the sample, some widows were not involved in business until they lost their husbands. "I lost my husband and needed money to take care of my children", testified a widow who operates a restaurant. Also, as reported by one other single respondent who owns a hair dressing saloon, she got into business as a way out of hardship caused as a result of the death of her father. "I went into business because I had no one to turn to as I lost my dad". This highlights the centrality of changes in one's personal life situation in terms of the death of a relation or the main earner or breadwinner, on entrepreneurs' choice of starting a business and becoming self-employed. Other responses such as unemployment, love of business (hobby), encouragement from family, the need for (extra) income for household needs, and the need for personal income were suggested by respondents as other motives for going into business.

For the few entrepreneurs (20%) who are motivated into MSE activities by the 'love for business', it is clear that these entrepreneurs became self employed by emulating their parents who acted as role models. The liking for business is generated and developed because one of the parents was also involved in a business or self-employment. One of the respondents, a second hand clothes vendor, confirmed that she was motivated into business by the fact that her mother was also an entrepreneur. "I have always liked business as this is what my Mom used to do for a living". For another respondent, a restaurant operator with access to enterprise support,

although she was pushed into business by the small and irregular salary she received as an auxiliary ward servant with the Baptist mission hospital, she was also motivated into business by the fact that her mother was a business woman.

"I worked before for the Baptist mission at Acha as an auxiliary ward servant. I had little pay and will go for months without pay; my salary was small and irregular. I needed and preferred a constant flow of income even if small.... I have a love for business and copied from my parents. That's what My Mom did".

The above accounts and testimonies suggest that becoming an entrepreneur can also be influenced by one's family or social background in terms of the employment status of family members especially parents. It is therefore likely that some entrepreneurs are motivated into self-employment by the fact that their parents were also self-employed.

Also, in relation to the above account given by a respondent in the sample, it is also very obvious that joblessness also poses as one of the fundamental factors that can influence one's choice of being self-employed. Other evidence from the in-depth interviews also shows that the increasing involvement of women in the MSE sector is either as a result of a job loss or retrenchment of the entrepreneur in question, a spouse or main breadwinner from formal sector or paid employment. According to a testimony by one of the respondents, she was pushed into operating an MSE activity because of the need for a job since she became unemployed through retrenchment. "I worked at the secretariat of the Ministry of Culture and Information and was terminated due to crisis at the Ministry. So I was forced to do business as it's the only means to have daily bread". Similarly, for another respondent who worked as a clerk and secretary with the National Produce Marketing Board (NPMB), the choice of creating an MSE activity was related to the need for employment or a job as she was pushed by "unemployment and joblessness" into the sector. "...because I lost my job with the NPMB I had to do something to earn money".

Another major concern and business motive of women in the MSE sector as revealed by results of the in-depth interview is the need to earn personal income and income for personal needs and children's (household) needs. Participants at the FGD and a number of interviewees have the same opinion on the need for personal income. According to respondents, income generating activities give women the opportunity to be independent by providing them with personal incomes and thus one of the major rationales for going into business. Some evidence also affirms the need for personal income for women as a positive step towards achieving autonomy and respect. Studies by other authors throw further light on the fundamental contribution of women's income to self-sufficiency and autonomy. Consistent with the research findings, a study in Sri Lanka observes changes in women's status and bargaining power resulting from setting up a business activity. The access to loans gave rise to independent incomes for female borrowers in Sri Lanka giving them more bargaining and decision making power within their households (Hulme and Mosley, 1996). Similarly, through self-employment and income earning activities, women in Bangladesh are able to achieve economic security through earning personal incomes (Kabeer, 2001; Holvoet, 2004). Unfortunately, growth in personal and independent income and positive changes in bargaining power is usually observed for less than half of borrowers. In effect, despite the positive changes enumerated and examined, women by and large remain trapped in a web of poverty. Also, as shown on Table 7 above, an average of 24.5% of entrepreneurs in the sample are encouraged into MSE activities by a family member; "I was particularly motivated by my elder sister who is also in this business" observed an entrepreneur. In the same way, another female entrepreneur also indicated that in addition to the fact that she liked tailoring or dress making, she was also motivated into the MSE activity by her sister saying, "I liked tailoring and my sister encouraged me into it". Other studies on the motive of women entrepreneurs in Cameroon and Tanzania provide similar outcomes with some differences. An analysis of the determinants and *raison d'être* of women's involvement in business in the South West province of Cameroon reveal that entrepreneurs by and large are compelled by economic hardship to operate informal MSE activities (Fonchingong, 2005:248; Niger-Thomas, 2001:45). Fonchingong and Niger-Thomas emphasize that particularly during the period (the 1990s) of declining economic opportunities, many women were forced to turn to self employment to make up for household income. On the other hand, an ILO report (2003:19) established that in Tanzania the most well-known and prevalent motive and determinant of women's entry into MSE activity is to "create employment for the woman herself."

Furthermore, some secondary reasons were also considered important by women as to why they have to operate a business activity. In order of priority, female entrepreneurs in the South West province of Cameroon get into business in order to subsidise household income and because they consider the business activity profitable (Fonchingong, 2005). In the same way, evidence from the accounts and reports of respondents presented by Figure 3 below, reveal that entrepreneurs get into business mainly because the business activity facilitates and enables them to supplement household income.

Figure 3: Distribution of respondents by reasons for starting up MSE
Source: Generated from field data

As to the reasons why women in the study sample set up MSE activities, the in-depth interviews and life histories propose the following: to subsidise household income (77.8%), because activities are easier to start (55.6%), because activities are profitable (40%), because MSE activity provides for survival (68.8%) and because of dropping out of school (44.4%). Firstly, women set up a particular MSE activity because they find such activities easier to start. The easy start up of WMSE activities could be threefold; either in terms of the ease of combining such activity with women's triple (reproductive, conjugal and productive) roles, or in terms of small initial capital or because no special skills are required. This is true for commercial activities, which made up a majority of MSE activities operated by female entrepreneurs in the study sample. From observation, the location of these enterprises is also characteristic of the principle of relative ease of entry reported by female entrepreneurs in the study sample. Some of the MSE activities indicated by female entrepreneurs as easy to set up such as restaurants are more or less a product of women's reproductive and domestic roles, which are less likely in need of professional training and high levels of education. As reported by one of the respondents to the in-depth interviews, her choice of a restaurant as an MSE activity is related to the principle of ease of entry. "I chose and preferred selling cooked food because I can cook very well and don't need to learn how to cook food; it's what I do for my family everyday", says an entrepreneur. Thus, women fit in better into the operation of enterprises with low skill requirements as these are more or less a reflection of their daily roles and duties.

Women's role of child bearing and rearing tend to restrict their mobility and thus the location of their business enterprises. Their enterprises are most commonly located near their homes making it possible for them to combine business and housework and child care (Fonchingong, 2005). In relation to the principle of ease of entry in terms of location of WMSE, the type of enterprises women run too, are those that give them the possibility to combine their double day and double roles of productive and reproductive work as can be seen by the testimony of one of the respondents to the in-depth interview below.

"I operated an off-license and a provision store before but decided to change to tailoring not because it is more profitable, but because it gives me more time to do my chores. I close my workshop when I want unlike the provision store where I am forced to stay on to sell all my perishables or the off-licence where you cannot close when you have customers".

This signifies that women's reproductive role restricts their choices of income earning opportunities. The flexibility required in terms of proximity to home on the whole compels female entrepreneurs to take up activities that are less profitable with low and limited returns.

The fact that women prefer a particular category of activities on the basis of ease of entry suggests and reiterates the fact that profit maximisation is not considered as the primary reason for setting up an MSE by women, though a substantial minority (40%) of respondents to the in-depth interview indicated that they were able to set up MSE activities because they considered such activities profitable. For (68.8%) of female entrepreneurs in the sample studied, a particular activity was set up because it provided survival in terms of basic

food needs to household members. As reported by one of the respondents, she preferred to sell food because even if she is unable to sell, her produce (food) will provide for consumption needs of household members. "I chose this business because even when I don't sell, I can still use the food to feed my children". For such entrepreneurs, they are satisfied when they are able to meet the food needs of household members regardless of whether any sales are done or not, indicating the importance of ensuring household survival needs as one of the primary reasons in making women set up and stay in business.

It is quite interesting that less than half (40%) of entrepreneurs consider profit maximisation as a reason for getting into business as shown on Figure 3 above. The rest (60%) of respondents did not consider business profitability, hence completely ignored the availability of a market for their services and/or produce as a major reason for setting up a particular business activity. This indirectly calls attention to the fact that little or no feasibility study is done by entrepreneurs in terms of the available market for their produce and services and the level of profitability of the activity in question, which is one of the reasons why there is a concentration of women into already saturated and consequently low return MSE activities with limited turnover and profit potential. Similarly, by ignoring the profit maximisation potential of a business activity also reveals limitations in women's entrepreneurial and business skills. On the other hand, it highlights women's emphasis on assuring basic household needs and ensuring survival as a significant rationale for setting up an MSE activity with little or no considerations for profit maximisation. However, to achieve the goal of ensuring survival warrants profitability of the business, which appears to be a major drawback to the potential of WMSE activity in reducing household poverty. This discrepancy in female entrepreneurs' business practice and skills in the long term explains the extensive complaint of competition, limited market for goods and services and very low returns as some of the major obstacles of female entrepreneurs.

The MSE sector also significantly provides an easy avenue for self employment for unskilled women and women with low or no educational qualifications and requirements for employment in formal sector jobs. As can be seen in Figure 3 above, 44% of female entrepreneurs in the study sample went into MSE activities because of the inability to continue schooling. One of the fundamental causes of limited formal sector employment opportunities for women is the relatively lower levels of education for women than men. Generally, for financial and socio-cultural reasons, girls have relatively lower enrolment and higher dropout rates from school and consequently lower levels of education than boys (Fonjong, 2001). As a result of this limitation in terms of relatively lower levels of education, some female entrepreneurs were pushed into MSE activities mainly because they were unable to continue school and were forced to drop out of school because of lack of money, and consequently could not obtain any paid formal sector job. "I went into business because my parents could not afford to pay for my education; I dropped out of school and needed to be occupied. I also wanted to raise money to be able to go back to school" said a 23 years old hairdresser without access to enterprise support, who left college in form 3. Another 23 year old seamstress without who dropped out of school because of lack of money also said "I got into business to be able to raise money and go back to school". Similarly, according to another interviewee, "I could not go to secondary school because of lack of money and so I was forced to do business as the only way to earn an income for myself". For this other respondent, because she dropped out of school after two years of secondary school, self employment also remained the only other alternative for earning an income. "I left school in form 2 so the only way to earn a living is through business".

4. CONTRIBUTING TO HOUSEHOLD WELFARE NEEDS: THE ROLE OF WMSE

Creating micro and small scale enterprises has increasingly become the mainstay of poor women entrepreneurs who are compelled to operate these enterprises for household provisioning and as a means of creating employment for themselves. Generally, women's ability to provide for basic household needs is considered by respondents in the sample as a major benefit and attributed first and foremost to the ability to run an enterprise. Access to micro credit accomplished through access to enterprise support programmes makes available business capital, giving entrepreneurs the opportunity to perform income earning activities and/or stay in business. All respondents to the in-depth interview regardless of access to enterprise support status, indicated a change in living standards as a result of the running of a micro enterprise. Entrepreneurs reported the use of income earned from their enterprises to meet basic survival needs of food, oil, salt, soap and other basic daily household needs. They also contribute in paying their children's healthcare, fees, books and other school needs. It is evident that through the running of their micro enterprises, women are able to make substantial contributions in sustaining the livelihood of their families.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents in the sample by use of income earned

Various needs met by income from WMSEs	Percentage
Basic Food needs	100
Clothing	75
Reinvest	48
Education	90
Savings	80
Health	80
Household Assets	60
Bills	60

Source: Generated from field Data

In relation to the main response rates indicated in Figure 3 above, for most entrepreneurs, running an MSE activity provides food needs of household members as confirmed by one of the respondents; 'My family has sufficient food and there is more regular payment of fees for my children than before'. For another, clothing and feeding her family is of utmost important and a benefit obtained through the setting up of an MSE activity: 'clothing and feeding for my family is more sufficient and better now than before'. For some, a general improvement in living standard is observed as a result of operating an MSE activity. "My family's living standard has improved now than before; I can take care of my family's health (medicines) needs" Similarly, a widow in the sample reported that she can readily supply survival needs of her children through income earned from MSE activities: 'I can buy my children's needs with ease now'.

The above is evidence of women's concern and the fact that WMSE activities set out to provide for basic household consumption needs. The distribution of roles and the contribution of women in meeting household needs affirm the centrality of women and WMSE activities in achieving and ensuring better living standards for household members. Thus, operating MSE activities has a trickledown effect on the survival and welfare needs of other household members, particularly children. As noted earlier, women are considered to be more altruistic and express a greater propensity to spend more of their income earned on household welfare needs of family members and children (Batiwala and Dhanraj, 2004; Kevane and Wydick, 2001; Mayoux, 1995). The provision of basic household needs is typically a woman's responsibility in most households. Women constantly provide for the family's needs and are able to provide support and supplement the needs of children, either neglected or not met by men. Thus, the contribution of women to the survival and livelihood of their families cannot be over emphasised. Women supply food, clothing, health needs and even education, which is more likely the man's responsibility, principally because they are involved in an MSE activity.

Extensive evidence from the sample draws attention to the fundamental role and contribution of women to human capital development through the operation of micro enterprises. Women's input in the development of the human capital needs of children and other household members in the form of education and schooling are quite significant. Running an MSE activity has proven to affect women's decisions with respect to the schooling of children especially females. As shown on Table 8 above, on average 90% of all respondents invested income earned from MSE activities into meeting the educational needs of household members. While Wydick (1999) and Kevane and Wydick (2001) specifically report and confirm a positive relationship between access to credit and women's increasing investment on children's education, the study demonstrates a widespread input of women's MSE activities (with and without access to credit) on children's schooling and educational needs. Providing for children's schooling and educational needs (fees, uniforms, books and pens) is a major concern for all respondents and this was ranked as top priority for the use of income earned from MSE activities. To illustrate women's awareness, support and recognition of the importance of education, women increasingly substitute children's labour, which is used predominantly during holidays. Thus the withdrawal and drop out of children from school for the purpose of supplying labour to WMSE is less likely. This may occur as a result of lack of funds and inability to pay fees and other needs and not because of the former.

CONCLUSION

As the study suggests, WMSEs are a primary mode of employment and major source of income for female entrepreneurs in the study. By making income available for household survival and wellbeing, these micro enterprises are therefore vital in enhancing the living standards of household members. Although WMSE activities provide a major outlet for employment and economic participation for women and the poor, these activities can generally be categorised as low skilled with low returns. Looking at the role of WMSE activities as a

means of generating employment, the focus of other studies has often been on self employment. The fact that WMSEs are mostly sole proprietorships (see Mead and Liedholm, 1998; Liedholm, 2002) and frequently use either apprentice and/or unpaid family labour, these studies overlook this as a limitation for enterprises to generate substantial employment for other women. The available evidence in the study sample shows that WMSE activities are predominantly sole proprietorships and enterprises with up to five employees both paid and unpaid.

Focusing on the productivity of micro enterprises, evidence from other studies observes a positive relationship between the size of an MSE and its productivity. Mead and Liedholm (1998), Liedholm (2002) and Mayoux (1995), argue that larger enterprises with more employees are better off and more productive. Thus, the size (micro scale and sole proprietorships) of a greater majority of WMSEs in the study define their productivity, which as observed are generally low return. I do argue here however, that despite the small scale of operations, coupled with low returns as observed in the study, these activities are capable of providing income for meeting basic household needs. The size of MSE activities has long been a major driving force behind the exclusion of such business activities from formal channels and existing mechanisms for acquiring financial resources (Mead and Liedholm, 1998; Mayoux, 1995; Montgomery and Weiss, 2005). For instance, the limitations often observed by MSE activities in general pertaining to lack of access to credit and resources are determined inter alia by the scale and size of these activities. But despite the size of WMSEs in the study, they were instrumental in meeting basic household needs.

A combination of factors is responsible for women's decision to operate an MSE activity. Some studies assert that the easy start up, small initial capital and limited skill requirement of WMSE activities are primarily responsible for the influx of women and the poor into these activities (Mayoux, 1995; Mead and Liedholm, 2002; Osirim, 2003). It emerged from the study that operating WMSEs is significantly reinforced by entrepreneurs' personal and family lives in association with insecurity and vulnerability. The data revealed that the desire to earn income for household needs was the major incentive behind women's entry into MSE activities. In relation to the need for income to ensure survival, women are also spurred to operate these enterprises by social pressures and changes in their personal life such as the lack of or loss of a major bread winner (husband or father), and/or work situation. In sum, the move into operating an MSE activity is mainly to address an urgent need or crisis evoked by hardship. In response to financial hardship and threats of insecurity, that are in part due to changes in the structure of the household, starting and operating an MSE activity increases the portfolio of economic activities available to female micro entrepreneurs and generates an income earning opportunity for the household. Through these activities therefore, female entrepreneurs are certain of a mechanism through which existing financial and other difficulties and/or those that may arise as a result of their vulnerability can be addressed and/or handled.

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